

8T – SUSY and Invariant Three

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants equation, which already allowed the unification of the first three interactions at $24 + 2$ variations, author argues for previously mentioned fact, that the modification cannot be performed on the invariant three as it is isomorphic to the Boson of the weak interaction.

Introduction

The main equation of the 8T is describing the variation of a Lorentz manifold, which according to the second equation (1.1) can be expressed as being part of a manifold packet. Such a theoretical construction manifested in one equation, is able to provide an answer to three major questions at the heart of major cosmology. The flatness puzzle, the "dark energy" puzzle and the "dark matter" puzzle by (1.2).

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_m - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_n = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The alignment of the first three interactions was based upon aligning the net variations, which stand for Bosons according to theorem two, which is part of three theorems that yielded the primorial. The alignment was presented in two ways, for simplicity sake the author will present only the second as it is simpler. The alignment is due to two real net variations going from the photon to the Gluon.

$$8 + (1) + 2 : [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3$$

$$8 + (1) + 2 \rightarrow 8 + (3)$$

$$8 + 3 : [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)^-] + \gamma \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)^-] + W^-$$

$$[8 + (g + 2)] \rightarrow [8 + (W^-)]$$

We said that the modification could not affect the invariant three, which is the electron. The reason it cannot effect the electron is because it is isomorphic to the Bosons of the first interaction, as both are represented by the same number, and in particle physics one of the Bosons of the weak interaction carry the same charge as the electron.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$3 \equiv (3)$$

$$(e)^- = W^-$$

Therefore, a modification on the electron is identical to modification on the alignment Boson which is in the case of the first three interactions is the Weak interaction. The only term in which the net variations unbound can modify on the third term than. Is the first term. It is important to emphasize, as reader may rightfully ask why the modification cannot affect the lepton. As a result of those exclusions on the Lepton and the Boson the only modification which is allowed will result in alignment at:

$$(8 * 3) + 2 = 26$$

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Okad's Theory